

A STUDY ON THE POSSIBLE SOURCES OF HOSPITAL-ACQUIRED PATHOGENS LEADING TO CAESAREAN WOUND INFECTION IN TIKRIT TEACHING HOSPITAL, IRAQ

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hospital-acquired infections are infections usually develop after 48 h of admission .to a hospital Surgical site infections of caesarean section are among the most common healthcare. Caesarean sections are the most frequently performed surgical operations all over the world. The present attempt was a prospective study which was carried out to determine the incidence of post-caesarean infections in Tikrit teaching hospital. **Materials and Methods:** The samples collected from patients, hospital staff, hospital environment and in-use disinfectant were transported to laboratory within one hour and processed for isolation and identification of pathogens associated with these samples. **Results:** The present study revealed that *S. aureus* was the commonest organism isolated from the patient's different sites and its frequency of isolation was 17.8%. The present study showed that the nurse uniforms were highly contaminated with *S. aureus* and *Ps. aeruginosa*

and the frequency of their isolation was 17.5 and 12.5% respectively. *P. aeruginosa* was the most common organism contaminated hospital environment and the frequency of its isolation from the hospital floor was 21.7%. **Conclusions:** The analysis included 95% confidence intervals for the total prevalence of each bacterial type. The exponential decay curve a decreasing trend in sample proportion as bacterial count increases. above models the

percentage of urine samples (from 100 patients) as a function of bacterial Total Viable Count (TVC/ml). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the P-values of the present programmed demonstrated highly significant differences for all bacteria suggesting a variation in prevalence with sites.

KEYWORDS: caesarean section, cross-infection, bacteria, Tikrit hospital, Iraq.

INTRODUCTION

Infections which are develop during a hospital stay without indication or sign revealing that they are present or incubating at of admission time are known as a nosocomial or hospital-acquired infections(HAIs). Hospital-acquired infections are infections usually develop after 48 h of admission to a hospital.^[1] These infections cause a significant issue of investigation particularly in low-income countries because they are contributing to high morbidity and mortality rates.^[2] HAIs usually affect almost 100 million patients all over the world,^[3] and the annual burden of HAIs in developed countries suggests that 4 million patients are affected by these infectious diseases.^[4,5] In India only as it was estimated by a WHO study in 2021 the attributable mortality rate of HAIs in intensive care units (ICUs) was 11%.^[6] Hospital-acquired infections are quite common and they cause discomfort to patients and lead to longer stay in the hospital which mean waste of time, manpower and money. Hospital acquired infections are among the most concern complications associated with modern medical therapy, that directly influenced by the high usage of invasive medical devices, misuse of antimicrobial therapy, patient age, and immunological status.^[7] Microorganisms causing hospital acquired wound infections could be obtained from patient Himself (endogenous), from hospital staff or contaminated objects in the hospital environment (exogenous). Most of these organisms are drug resistant and this resistance might be resulted extensive use of antibiotics in the hospital.^[8,9,10] Surgical site infections of caesarean section are among the most common healthcare. Caesarean sections are the most frequently performed surgical operations all over the world. The reported rates of wound of caesarean section infection among 73 cases studied ranged from 2.0%–56.0%, which were highly heterogeneous, when only 11.0% showed a surgical site infection rate above 20.0%. Surgical site infections mostly surfaced within two-weeks after section. The strongest and frequently cited risk factors of wound infections were duration of labour ≥ 8 h, surgical duration, multiple examinations of vagina, stored water usage, and premature rupture of membrane.^[11]

The present attempt was a prospective study which was carried out to determine the incidence of post-caesarean infections in Tikrit teaching hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients

This study was carried out in teaching hospital of Tikrit. The present work was conducted on 100 patients with caesarean sections. The acceptance for participation in the present study was taken from all the participants whose native language is Arabic. They were not mentally retarded and they were completely healthy considering hearing and speaking.

Isolation of bacteria

The samples collected from patients, hospital staff, hospital environment and in-use disinfectant were transported to laboratory within one hour and processed as follow:

1. Groin samples and samples from hands of hospital staff were enriched in nutrient broth at 37 °C for 18 hours. Each sample was sub-cultured on blood agar, MacConkey agar and pseudomonas selective agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The suspected colonies were purified twice and the isolates were identified.^[10]
2. Nasal swabs were inoculated on blood agar and mannitol salt agar and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The suspected colonies were purified twice and identified as mentioned elsewhere.^[12]
3. Urine samples were cultured by streaking 0.01 ml of urine with 4 mm diameter bacteriological loop onto blood agar plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Total viable counts (TVC) on each plate was done and counted as viable counts in the milliliter of urine.^[13]
4. Samples from patient's clothes, nurse uniforms, surgeon's masks, bedsheets and blankets were sub-cultured on blood agar plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours and the isolated colonies were purified on nutrient agar twice and identified following Al-Jebouri.^[13]
5. Surgical gloves and needles samples were enriched in brain-heart infusion broth for 18 hours at 37 °C. One ml quantity of each sample was sub-cultured on blood agar plate and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The suspected colonies were purified twice and identified.^[10]

6. Settled blood agar plates were used for sampling of the air which were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours and the total colony counts were enumerated. The total number of the air-borne bacteria per cubic meter were calculated according to method described elsewhere.^[14]
7. Floor samples were enriched in nutrient broth for 18 hours at 37 °C and each sample was sub-cultured on blood agar plates. The suspected colonies were purified twice on nutrient agar and identified following method mentioned by Al-Jebouri *et al.*^[10]
8. Tap water samples were enriched in nutrient broth at 37 °C and incubated at room temperature for three days. One standard pipette drop from each culture was spread onto blood agar plate and incubated at 37 °C and incubated at room temperature for overnight.^[15] The suspected colonies were purified twice and identified.^[10]
9. The sample of disinfectants was 0.1 ml was taken from in-use disinfectant solution which was inactivated by adding the sample to 5 ml nutrient broth and incubated at 37 °C for 18 hours. A loopful from each tube was streaked on the surface of blood agar, MacConkey agar and pseudomonas selective agar and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The suspected colonies were purified twice and identified.^[16]

RESULTS

Bacteria isolated from patients

Table 1 shows the isolation frequency of the four bacterial types isolated from different sites of the patients. The total isolation rate of *S. aureus* was almost 18%, while the frequency of isolation of *Ps. aeruginosa*, *E.coli* and *Proteus spp.* was 12.1, 6.5 and 4.7% respectively. Almost 40% of the samples collected from groin, nose, clothes of the patients were contaminated with infectious bacteria. Patient's groin was the most source of infectious agents (58.4%). 17% of samples taken from the nose of patients were *S. aureus* positive whereas only 3% of the specimens revealed *Ps. aeruginosa*. The forest plot model of analysis included 95% confidence intervals for the total prevalence of each bacterial type (Figure 1). The error bars reflected uncertainty statistics around estimated prevalent proportions assumed binomial distribution. The presented plot of Figure 1 revealed a clearer picture of the precision and potential variability of the rates of prevalence.

The total viable counts of bacteria isolated from urine of 100 patients with caesarean wounds were presented in Table 2. 12% of urine samples tested showed more than 10⁵ cfu/ml of urine which indicated a bacteriuria. The exponential decay curve a decreasing trend in sample

proportion as bacterial count increases. above models the percentage of urine samples (from 100 patients) as a function of bacterial Total Viable Count (TVC/ml). The statistical goodness-of-fit values for the exponential decay model revealed R-squared equal to 0.701 indicating a moderate good fit with deviation from the actual data(Figure 2).

Table 1: Bacteria isolated from patient’s sites other than caesarean wound.

Bacteria	Patient’ site			Total (n=214)
	Groin(n=54)	Nose(n=100)	Clothes(n=60)	
	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)	No.(%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	6(11.1)	17(17)	15(25)	38(17.8)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	12(22.2)	3(3)	11(18.3)	26(12.1)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14(25.9)	0	0	14(6.5)
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	5(9.2)	0	5(8.3)	10(4.7)
Total	37(58.4)	20(20)	31(51.6)	88(41.1)

Figure 1: Forest plot shows bacterial prevalence with 95% confidence intervals.

Table 2: Total viable count of bacteria isolated from urine of 100 patients with caesarean wound.

Total viable count (TVC)/ml	Urine samples
	No.(%)
$\leq 10^3$	34(34)
10^4	54(54)
$\geq 10^5$	12(12)

Figure 2: Exponential decay curve of bacteria count in urine samples.

Bacteria isolated from medical staff

Table 3 shows the isolation frequency of different organisms isolated from medical staff which reveals that *S. aureus* was the most frequent with rate of isolation was 15.4%. The frequency of isolation of *E.coli*, *Ps. aeruginosa* and *Proteus spp.* was 9.9, 6.9 and 1.2% respectively. Nurses uniforms showed the most frequent contamination by the bacteria under study particularly with *S. aureus* and *Ps. aeruginosa*. Surgeon’s gloves and masks revealed also different rates of contamination by *S. aureus* and *E.coli* but neither *Ps. aeruginosa* nor *Proteus spp.* were isolated. The combined linear and exponential fit chart analyses was plotted for each bacteria across the four medical staff sites which were hands, uniforms, gloves, masks(Figure 3). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) P-values of the present programmed demonstrated highly significant differences for all bacteria suggesting a variation in prevalence with sites.

Table 3: Distribution of bacteria isolated from medical staff including doctors and nurses.

Bacteria	Site of Collection				Total (n=162)
	Nurse hands (n=5)	Nurse uniforms (n=40)	Surgeon’s gloves (n=40)	Surgeon’s masks (n=32)	
	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	8(16)	7(17.5)	5(12.5)	5(15.5)	25(15.4)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	6(12)	5(12.5)	0	0	11(6.9)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	8(16)	2(5)	2(5)	4(12.5)	16(9.9)
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	0	2(5)	0	0	2(1.2)
Total	22(41)	16(40)	7(17.5)	9(28)	54(33.3)

Figure 3: Linear and exponential fit chart analysis of the different bacteria considered.

Bacteria isolated from hospital environment

Table 4 shows isolation frequency of the four bacterial types from hospital environment. *Ps. aeruginosa* was the most frequent with total isolation rate almost 13%. The total isolation rate of *E.coli*, *Proteus spp.* and *S. aureus* was 10.5, 1.2 and 5.7% respectively. Floor of the hospital revealed frequent contamination with *Ps. aeruginosa* and *E.coli* with frequency of isolation was 21.7 and 20% respectively. Blankets and bedsheets showed various degrees of contamination with *Ps. aeruginosa* with rate of isolation 11.7 and 26% respectively. *S. aureus* and *E.coli* were frequently isolated from surgical needles with frequency of isolation was 8.3 and 5% respectively. But no *Proteus* was isolated surgical needles. Tap water samples showed various degrees of contamination with *Ps. aeruginosa* and *E.coli* with frequencies did not exceed 17%. No *S. aureus* nor *Proteus spp.* were isolated from hospital waters. No growth was seen of any organisms to be isolated from 25 unused surgical gloves. The funnel plot demonstrated the proportion of bacterial isolates in the hospital environment in relevance to sample size with 95% confidence limits. *Ps. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* were near or slightly above the upper limit demonstrating a potentially higher than expected prevalence (Table 4, Figure 4).

Table 4: Distribution of bacteria isolated from hospital environment.

Bacteria	Site of collection						Total (n=162)
	Floor (n=60)	Blankets (n=60)	Bed sheets (n=50)	Tap Water (n=60)	Surgical needles (n=60)	Surgical gloves before use (n=25)	
	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	NO.(%)	
<i>S. aureus</i>	4(6.6)	4(6.6)	5(10)	5(8.3)	0	0	18(5.7)
<i>Ps aeruginosa</i>	13(21.7)	7(11.7)	13(26)	1(1.7)	6(10)	0	40(12.7)
<i>E.coli</i>	12(20)	4(6.6)	4(8)	3(5)	10(16.6)	0	33(10.5)
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	3(5)	1(1.7)	0	0	0	0	4(1.2)
Total	32(53.3)	16(26.6)	22(44)	9(15)	16(26.6)	0	0

Figure 4: Funnel plot of bacteria in hospital environment.

Table 5 shows the total viable counts of organisms/m³ monthly isolated from 100 air samples of the surgical theatre. It was found that 34% of air samples were containing mean number of 100 ml cfu/m³ whereas only 3% of samples contained 1100 cfu/m³. The samples during second month of the study showed high percent of contamination, and the frequency of samples contained 900 cfu/m³ and 1100 cfu/m³ of air were 35 and 10 respectively. The 2nd, 3rd, and 4th months revealed clear exponential decay behavior (moderate b values), whereas the 1st and 5th months demonstrated unstable fit parameters i.e. very small b, large a/c indicated limited exponential characteristics or inconsistent data(Tables 5,6; Figure 5). The 3rd and 4th months revealed excellent fit ($R^2 \geq 0.83$), but 1st month has a reasonably good fit. The 2nd and 5th months showed weak fit with low R^2 with value equal to 0.133 indicating the

exponential model with different distribution and colonization of bacteria at those months (Table 6). Hundred samples from in-use disinfectants like chloroxylenol, chlorhexidine, savlon and providine-iodine were examined (Table 7). *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus spp.* were not detected in these chemicals under use at time of sampling. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was isolated from chlorhexidine and chloroxylenol and the frequency of isolation was 20 and 4 respectively. *E.coli* was also isolated from chlorhexidine and providine-iodine with frequencies of 8 and 16 respectively

Table 5: Total viable counts(TVC's) of bacteria monthly isolated from air of hospital for five times.

Mean cfu /m ³	Total viable count of bacteria isolated from air of surgical theatre (n=20)					Total No.(%)
	1 st month	2 nd month	3 rd month	4 th month	5 th month	
	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	
100	5(25)	4(20)	12(60)	8(40)	5(25)	34(34)
300	8(40)	7(35)	5(25)	6(30)	0	26(26)
500	4(20)	0	2(10)	1(5)	8(26)	15(15)
700	3(15)	0	1(5)	3(15)	6(30)	13(13)
900	0	7(35)	0	2(10)	0	9(9)
1100	0	2(10)	0	0	1(5)	3(3)
Total	20(100)	20(100)	20(100)	20(100)	20(100)	100(100)

Figure 5: The exponential decay curve analysis across five months (Table 5) models the relationship between airborne bacterial counts (TVC in cfu/m³) and their corresponding monthly percentages.

Table 6: Summary of Exponential Fit Parameters.

Month	a (Initial)	b (Decay rate)	c (Asymptote)	R ²
1st month	104,208	~0.00000034	-104,169.7	0.755
2nd month	15.07	0.00373	13.42	0.059
3rd month	93.02	0.00422	-1.06	0.999
4th month	51.88	0.00252	0.49	0.836
5th month	38,117	~0.00000036	-38,094.88	0.133

Table 7: Total viable counts(TVC's) of bacteria isolated from 100 sample of in-use disinfectants of hospital.

Bacteria	Disinfectant in-use				Total No.(%)
	Chloroxylenol	Chlorhexidine	Savlon	Providine-iodine	
	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	No.(%)	
E.coli	0	8(8)	0	16(16)	24(24)
<i>Ps.aeruginosa</i>	4(4)	20(20)	0	0	24(24)
<i>S. aureus</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4(100)	28(28)	0	16(16)	48(48)

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that *S. aureus* was the commonest organism isolated from the patient's different sites and its frequency of isolation was 17.8%. In contrast, Al-Jebouri and his co-workers found that E.coli was the most common organism isolated from patient's sites with isolation frequency almost 6%.^[10] The isolation frequency of *S. aureus* from the nose of patients was higher (17%) compared to the isolation frequency of *Ps. aeruginosa*. In contrast, it was concluded elsewhere that Gram-negative bacilli were isolated more frequently than *S. aureus* from patient's nasal swab.^[17] Two studies revealed that *S. aureus* was isolated from nasal swabs of patients with frequency of 13 and 17.8% respectively.^[16] It was found recently a lack in literature concerning bacterial profile which was a weakness of knowledge of microbial flora causing wound infection of caesarean section. It was concluded that only 1.0% of laboratories in SSA are formally assigned in delivering of bacterial testing.^[18] Meanwhile, Wood showed that their data highlights *Staphylococcus aureus* as the more prevalent reported pathogen causing SSI aligning with data a recently concluded from meta-analysis.^[19] Surgical caesarean section is area of concern considering reported rates of Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*. Distribution of Gram-negative bacilli like *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *E. coli* also emphasizes the burden of enterobacteria in SSI.^[20] The present study utilized the forest plot model of analysis included 95% confidence intervals for the total prevalence of each bacterial type. The error bars reflected uncertainty statistics around

estimated prevalent proportions assumed binomial distribution. The data plotted revealed a clearer picture of the precision and potential variability of the rates of prevalence. However, The principle indication for caesarean section among women who developed SSI was previous caesarean section, which is usually followed by severe oligohydramnios. The follow-up of 30-day revealed a significantly higher risk of SSI among women whose wounds were closed using subcutaneous sutures and whose section lasted less than 30 min, with the risk becoming more pronounced after 15 days post-operation.^[21]

Moreover, in the present study, 12% of caesarean sectioned women urine showed $>10^5$ cfu/ml which indicated bacteriuria, whereas other study concluded that the frequency of bacteriuria was not more than 7.8% of women with caesarean section. The higher incidence of bacteriuria concluded by the present study possibly due to urine stasis and/or to frequent use of urinary catheters for patients with difficult operations. This might provide a proper medium for the organisms to grow. The statistical goodness-of-fit values for the exponential decay model revealed R-squared equal to 0.701 indicating a moderate good fit with deviation from the actual data. In, addition, the artificial introducing of the organisms to urinary tract might cause bacteriuria.^[22] Catheterized patients have higher possibility of HAIs in the surgical ward and ICU than non-catheterized patients. This may be attributed to catheter-associated infections secondary to contamination. Patients who stay longer in the hospital have greater opportunity of acquiring infections compared with those discharged early. Prolonged length of stay in hospital can increase exposure to various microorganisms including pathogens acquiring from hospital environment, thereby increasing the prevalence of infections.^[23]

S. aureus was the most frequent organism isolated from medical staff, and the isolation rate of this organism was almost 15%. The others workers found a higher isolation frequency of this organism (28.5%) from people working in the hospital wards.^[24] The isolation frequency of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* from nurse hands was similar. In contrast, Al-Jebouri et al. found that the isolation frequency of *S. aureus* and *E.coli* from nurse hand were 0 and 18% respectively.^[10] In a study conducted on carriage of *S. aureus* and Gram-negative bacilli by hands of medical personnel, it was found that the isolation frequency of both organisms was 11 and 41% respectively.^[25] The high isolation frequency of pathogenic bacteria from hands of hospital personnel possibly due to poor handwashing practices by medical personnel which subsequently lead to a high nosocomial infection.^[20] Furthermore, The analysis of microbial flora including a quantitative and qualitative assessment using the heterotrophic plate total

bacterial count (HTBC) at 37°C and 22°C for coliforms or *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Enterococci*, *Staphylococci*, Gram-negative bacteria and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The isolated strains were typed through standardized miniaturized tunnels for biochemical analytical profile index tests. A selection for the microorganisms that are most frequently associated with the occurrence of HAIs was made.^[26]

The present study showed that the nurse uniforms were highly contaminated with *S. aureus* and *Ps. aeruginosa* and the frequency of their isolation was 17.5 and 12.5% respectively. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) P-values of the present programmed demonstrated highly significant differences for all bacteria suggesting a variation in prevalence with sites. In comparison, other study found that 14% of nurse uniforms become contaminated with *S. aureus*.^[27] In addition, Noone et al. found that 33.5% of nurse uniforms become contaminated with *Ps. aeruginosa* especially after handling of colonized patients.^[21] These results indicate that the nurses uniforms could be an important route of cross-infection between the patients. The present study showed that *S. aureus* is the commonest organism contaminating surgeon's mask and the frequency of its isolation was 15.5%. On the other hands, others found that 31.9% of surgeon's mask were *S. aureus* positive.^[20] The high rate of mask contamination with *S. aureus* is possibly due to high rate of nasal carriers among hospital personnel. Surgeon's gloves also showed frequent contamination with *S. aureus* and this was almost similar to other studies findings.^[26]

The present study revealed that *P. aeruginosa* was the most common organism contaminated hospital environment and the frequency of its isolation from the hospital floor was 21.7%. The funnel plot demonstrated the proportion of bacterial isolates in the hospital environment in relevance to sample size with 95% confidence limits. *Ps. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* were near or slightly above the upper limit demonstrating a potentially higher than expected prevalence whereas its isolation frequency from floors of general hospitals in Diwania and Najaf cities were 8 and 10% respectively.^[27] The high rate of contamination of floor found in the present study could be due to lack of strict supervision particularly during visiting times to patients which are lacking of restriction and control. The *Ps. aeruginosa* frequently contaminated blankets and bedsheets and the rates of isolation were 11.7 and 26% respectively. Other workers found less isolation frequency of the same organism from the both sites. *S. aureus* was frequently isolated from surgical needles (8.3%) which was almost similar to those found elsewhere.^[28] *E. coli* was the most common organism isolated from tap water samples. Its

frequency of isolation was 16.6%. In contrast, Werry et al. could not isolate this organism from tap water samples of hospital.^[29] The present results possibly indicated tap water pollution. However, no any sample taken from clean surgical gloves showed positive bacterial growth. *Ps. aeruginosa* was isolated from in-use samples of chlorhexidine and chloroxylenol with frequency of 20 and 4% respectively. In comparison, Al-Jebouri and Yehia found out that the isolation rate of the same organism from chlorhexidine was 4.1% and chloroxylenol was free of this pathogen in the maternity hospital of Mosul city.^[30] Other work carried out elsewhere showed that in-use solutions of hibitane and savlon were frequently contaminated with *Ps. Aeruginosa*.^[8] *E. coli* showed frequency of presence in chlorhexidine and providine-iodine 8 and 16 % respectively. In contrast, Al-Jebouri and yehia did not find this organism in disinfectants of maternity hospital.^[30] The high frequency of contamination of disinfectant solutions in-use with pathogenic bacteria found in the present study could be due to extensive use and misuse of these disinfectants even without disinfection policy. The role of airborne transmission of pathogenic bacteria has been extensively studied. In the present study, the mean total viable counts of bacteria (TVC)/m³ of air was 100-1100 cfu/m³ and the geometric mean was 452/m³. The 2nd and 5th months showed weak fit with low R² with value equal to 0.133 indicating the exponential model with different distribution and colonization of bacteria at those months. This was much higher than that found by other investigators who concluded that the geometric mean of bacteria in air was 70.3 cfu/m³.^[31] The highest geometric mean of bacteria found in the present study was not unexpected since a positive pressure ventilation was applied in the hospital and lack of strict hygiene conditions.

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Statement of Ethics

All the procedures involving human participation were conducted in strict accordance with ethical standards of Institutional Research Committee, Department of Scientific Research, Tikrit University as well as the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments or equivalent ethical norms.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise.

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Financial disclosure

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Author contributions

Mohemid Maddallah Al-Jebouri, suggested the protocol, reading, correction and supervision of the study; Hana Salman Al-Bayati, collection and analyses of data and manuscript draft writing.

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